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Code, data and trained DLC network for Suver et al. 2023 published in Current Biology.

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1/5/2023

We made sub-figures using functions in python (SuverEtAl2023_makeFigures.py) or one of several Matlab (.m) functions. To run this code, download and place in the same folder both SuverEtAl2023_Code and SuverEtAl2023_Data (file paths may need to be edited if using on a computer running Windows, rather than Linux). We generated the metadata in this data folder using functions included in SuverEtAl2023_plotting.py, from raw video files tracked using the DeepLabCut network included in SuverEtAl2023_DLC.